

Sintering experiments and luminescent properties of Zn²⁺ doped Y₂O₃.

Peter Švančárek, Robert Klement, Monika Micháľková and Dušan Galusek

FunGlass - Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovak Republic

(E-mail: peter.svancarek@tnuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

Y₂O₃ ceramics have been studied for many years because of their promising properties like high corrosion resistance, high melting point (2425°C), low thermal expansion coefficient and relatively high heat conductivity which can be critical for temperature management. Having cubic crystallographic unit, it is easier to create transparent ceramics since it is isotropic environment for electromagnetic radiation. Applications ranges from transparent windows to missile domes, bulb envelopes, and laser hosts^{1,2}. When compared to other transparent materials such as Al₂O₃, AlON and MgAl₂O₄ (spinel), the Y₂O₃ has a far lower emissivity and a smaller absorption coefficient in the IR part of spectra at elevated temperatures³. These characteristics make it an excellent IR window material for high-temperature applications.

The starting fine grained Y₂O₃ powder was produced by PENGDA with reported particle size of 150nm. Isopropanol based suspension was prepared with 5 vol% of yttria, stabilized by PEG (1wt% of yttria mass). Suspension was dispersed by ultrasonication for 8 minutes with cycle 5(discontinuous ultrasonication). Particle Size Analyzer (90Plus, f. Brookhaven) was used to determine the level of disperzation. Analysis showed that we had reached 558nm +- 55nm particle size which is far from mean grain size of 150nm declared by Pengda manufacturer and even further from grain size of about 80nm determined by SEM. Suspension was pressure filtrated at about 50 MPa pressure to obtain green body pellets. Then the pellets were dried in oven at 40°C for 12 hours.

Green body pellets underwent the sintering experiments in Netzsch TMA 402F1 in ambient atmosphere and vacuum with following regimes:

1. In air: 10°C/min to 1100°C; followed by 5°C/min to 1550°C and 1hour of dwell time. The free cooling in furnace followed. Graph 1a.
2. In vacuum: 10°C/min to 1350°C and 2hours of dwell time followed by free cooling. Graph 1b.

After sintering, the homogeneity of sintered specimens was evaluated visually with help of crossing light. The density (measured in water) reached 98.4% at sintering in air and 98% at sintering in vacuum. This difference was probably observed because of the settleable temperature at vacuum sintering was 200°C less than the settleable temperature at air sintering.

SEM images (Fig.1a and 1b) have shown fine microstructure without pores. Paradoxically, the median particle size was observed to be smaller for specimen sintered in air at 1550°C. It could be explained by length of dwell time after reaching the end density during sintering which was two times longer for vacuum sintered specimen compared to air sintered specimen.

Fig.1a. SEM of in air sintered specimen

Fig.1b. SEM of in vacuum sintered specimen

First experiments with Zn^{2+} dopation were made by infiltration of presintered Y_2O_3 pellets. Presintering was made in ambient atmosphere using following regime: heating by the rate of $10^\circ C/min$ to $1000^\circ C$, dwell time 1 hour which was followed by free cooling. The density was measured based on dimensions of pellets and their mass. Concentrations of doping zinc acetate solutions were adjusted according to the porosity of presintered pellets. The level of dopation was adjusted to 0.25, 0.5, 1 and 2 at. % of Zn^{2+} . After 5 hours of infiltration, the pellets were dried and sintered using following regime: heating by the rate of $10^\circ C/min$ to $1400^\circ C$, dwell time 2 hours which was followed by free cooling.

Graph 2. XRD analysis

The XRD analysis was made to determine whether new phases had emerged during sintering Y_2O_3 with addition of ZnO (Graph 2). The main phase was identified as Y_2O_3 . There was also observed one relatively strong peak which might belong to orthorhombic ZnY_2O_4 phase⁴.

Preliminary fluorescence spectra measurements showed the broad band emission centered at around 555 nm (warm white light emission) when the samples were excited by 378nm UV radiation.

The future work plans involve the optimization of pellet infiltration by optically active metal cations, the optimization of sintering process and application of HIP to reach fully transparent specimens.

Keywords: Pressure filtration, Thermomechanical analysis, Y_2O_3 ceramics

Acknowledgment:

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566, SAS-MOST JRP 2015/6, VEGA 2/0026/17 and VEGA 1/0527/18.

References:

-
- ¹ An, A. Ito, T. Goto, Transparent yttria produced by spark plasma sintering at moderate temperature and pressure profiles, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 32 (2012) 1035–1040
 - ² H. Zhang, B.N. Kim, K. Morita, H. Yoshida, K. Hiraga, Y. Sakka, Fabrication of transparent yttria by high-pressure spark plasma sintering, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 94 (2011) 3206–3210
 - ³ M.E. Thomas, R.I. Joseph, W.J. Tropsf, Infrared transmission properties of sapphire, spinel, yttria, and ALON as a function of temperature and frequency, *Appl. Opt.* 27 (1988) 239–245
 - ⁴ Bidhu Bhusan Das, Venugopal Potu & Govinda Rao Rупpa, Synthesis, crystal structure and magnetic studies of ZnY_2O_4 oxide, *Indian Journal of Pure & Applied Physics* Vol. 53, June 2015, pp. 399-403